

Assessing Factors Influencing Information Technologies Project Performance at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter

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Abstract:

This study assessed the factors influencing information technologies project performance at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter. Specifically, the study assessed the associations between Human Resource Capabilities (HRC), Financial Resource Availability (FRA), Legal Framework Adherence (LFA) and Project Performance (PP) at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter. The study employed a cross-sectional survey research design to collect data from 136 employees at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter obtained through stratified sampling technique. The study used an online questionnaire and interviews for data collection. In addition, data were analyzed using

percentage and multiple linear regression through using SPSS Version 26 and Smart PLS Software Version 4. The study funding shows indirect relationship between HRC, FRA and PP, showing that Legal framework is a significant mediator of HRC, FRA and PP. framework adherence influence project performance at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter. Therefore, the factors influencing information technologies project performance at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter were human resource capabilities, financial resource availability and legal framework adherence. The study concluded that, the presence of human resource and financial resource should be regulated with existing legal frameworks for ensuring project performance. Therefore, the study recommended that, the Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter should invest in human resource and financial resource while ensuring existing legal frameworks are implemented.

Keywords: *Human Resource, Financial Resource, Legal Framework, Project Performance, Mediation.*

Introduction

Worldwide, organizations are struggling to ensure their projects are successfully using the available resources. This area has been paid attention to by researchers and scholars globally to determine the parameters for determining project success. Saridaki et al. (2019) suggested

that any project's success depends on the availability of resources that facilitate the implementation of its activities and operations. Thus, it's undeniable that resources are the basic foundations for the success of any project, either in public or private organizations (Raphael & Philip, 2016).

Various projects in African countries are implemented to achieve organizations' strategic goals while maximizing benefits as much as possible. This has been influenced by the need to manage resources effectively. In due course, the determination to succeed in these projects has become essential for the success of the existing projects (Nazia, Bilali, & Abdul, 2016). According to Ksae, Jonathan, and Hashemianfar (2018), there are no universal factors that determine project success. Thus, organizations in African countries should pay concern and attention when determining the success of project performance determinants.

In Tanzania, like any other developing country's IT projects, success has paid and received attention to the development of the country in health sectors, infrastructure sectors, and education, among others, to smooth the government's service provision and operations (Kazare, 2019). For instance, the Financial Management Information System (FMIS) and the Human Capital Information Management System (HCIMS) are among the initiatives and IT projects that the government of Tanzania has implemented. Other projects include construction projects, health sector projects, and education projects (Public Procurement Regulatory Authority, 2017).

Despite the effort and initiatives that the government of Tanzania has taken, some projects have failed to deliver as planned within reasonable time and cost while maintaining the required quality (PPR, 2017; URT, 2018; Kazare, 2019; Lusupi, 2020). For instance, studies and reports from PPRA and the Controller Audit General (CAG) revealed that most of the projects in Tanzania were not successful, including those of the Tanzania Police Force (Kazare, 2019, PPRA, 2017, and URT, 2018). Therefore, it is undeniable that there was a need for a study to assess the factors influencing information technology project performance at the Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter.

The Objective of this Study

1. To examine the effect of human resource capabilities on project performance at TPFAD.

2. To examine the effect of financial resource availability on project performance at TPFAD.

3. To examine the effect of legal frameworks adherence on project performance at TPFAD.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: A cross-sectional design was adopted to assess factors for project performance at Tanzania Police Force. This design was chosen to capture relevant information from various respondents who were directly/indirectly involved in project management at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter. The design involves collecting data from the sampled respondents once in the entire period of data collection.

Participants

The study participants consisted of employees working at the Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter. The inclusion criteria was employees who were available and dealing with Information Technologies Project during data collection at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter.

Data Collection Methods

The survey questionnaire was used in this study consisted of two parts. The first part collected demographic information from the participants, enabling a comprehensive understanding of their characteristics. The second part utilized a five-point Likert scale from 1 strongly agreeing to 5 strongly disagreeing to assess the dimension's human resources, financial resources, and project performance while considering the mediating influence of legal frameworks. Participants were asked to rate their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements related to scales.

Analysis

The collected data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Inferential statistical data analysis was done using Partial Least Square computed by Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) through Smart PLS

Version 4 for validation of the study model. The statistical method was employed to measure the relationship of the study variables where by a statistical significance level of 0.05 or lower was deemed appropriate for the p-value. In addition, the quantitative were presented using Frequency Distribution Tables.

Model Evaluation and Interpretation

The assumptions of reflective measurement model were verified through Factor Loadings,

Composite Reliability, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) to ensure the model relevancy.

Results

Based on the study model, bootstrap was used to obtain the p-values of the correlations between the HR, FR with moderating effect of LF on PP as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Hypothesized Variables

Indicators	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
FR_ -> LF_	0.683	0.684	0.077	8.836	0.000
HRC_ -> LF_	0.202	0.204	0.087	2.312	0.021
LF_ -> PP_	0.698	0.704	0.056	12.462	0.000

Table 1 finding shows three hypothesized relationships e.g., FR -> LF with p-value of 0.000, HRC -> LF with p-value of 0.021 and LF -> PP with p-value of 0.000 were supported (p-value <0.05) hence the hypothesis was accepted. Thus, the study funding shows indirect relationship between HRC, FRA and PP, showing that Legal framework is a significant mediator of HRC, FRA and PP. framework adherence influence project performance at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter.

Discussion

From the study findings, Financial Resource Availability has positive significance with Information Technologies Project Performance when mediating by Legal Frameworks Adherence which implies that Financial Resource Availability require viable Legal Frameworks Adherence in orders to archive information Technologies Project Performance in an organization. This implies a potential correlation financial resource availability and information technologies project performance. This finding is supported by Lusupi (2020) that adequate and availability of enough financial resource influence construction project

performance. Furthermore, financial resource availability is important for continuation and

In addition, Human Resource Capabilities was significance correlated with Information Technologies Project Performance when mediated by Legal Framework Adherence which implies that Human Resource Capabilities need rules and regulation to enhance ethical and best practices in project management.

This finding is in line with Lily et al. (2018) that, human resource capacity had positive influence on information technologies project performance as they are important for supporting the payment various project activities. The study recommended that there should be recruitment of competent employees who might influence project performance. Also, Rugiri and Njangiru (2018) on their study findings availability of resources e.g., human resources influence project performance. Thus, from this study it's clear that availability of resources has association with project performance.

Conclusion

This study concludes that, project performance is the determinants of various factors including

human resource, financial resource and legal frameworks. In addition, an organization needs human resource with abilities to perform their various projects activities influences project performance. This was also suggested with positive path coefficient with a positive significant influence of human resources capabilities with moderating effect of legal frameworks on project performance. On the other hand, it is concluded financial resources was statistically significant with a positive path coefficient moderated by legal frameworks towards project performance. This finding, suggest that, presence of financial resource assist the organization to performance various project activities under the presence of existing legal frameworks. Generally, resources availabilities such as human and financial are not enough to facilitates project performance, rather, having resources that are guided by rules and regulations enhance project performance as suggested from the study findings.

The results advise public organizations to consider financial resource and human resource in the project management strategy improving information technologies project performance. Additionally, the study is required to maximize suggestions and confirm the advantages of financial resource and human resource organization project on a larger scale.

Recommendations

Drawing from the findings and constraints of this investigation, it recommends that the subsequent actions be taken.

Significant change on how to utilize resources of the organizations. This can be done through active and continuous training and educating the project management stakeholders while ensuring legal framework which governs the system and the benefits it brings to the project management stakeholders, and also to the government. Additionally, to promote a holistic approach to resources management assessment should be included in routine of the organization activities of the organizations.

Limitations

The current study is subject to certain constraints. Initially, the study was carried out at Tanzania Police Force Head Quarter, thereby potentially constraining the applicability of the findings. Additionally, it is possible that time frameworks of this research may not provide sufficient time to fully investigating the study problem.

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